
IMPACT OF INTELLIGENCE GATHERING ON MINIMIZING SECURITY CHALLENGES IN SELECTED COMMUNITIES IN NORTH BANK, MAKURDI LGA

BY

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ABSTRACT

Safety of people living in the society is the concerned of the government. To achieve this aim, impactful security strategies are required. The study investigated the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in our communities in Benue state, Nigeria. Two (2) research questions guided the study. The study adopted the survey research design. Mainly residence of Angwa Ochonu Community, Ajetachi Community, Asase 1 and 2 Community, IDP Camp Community and Court 5 Community in Makurdi made up the population. 200 respondents were sampled for the study through multi-stage sampling procedure. A self-developed questionnaire called "Impact of Intelligence Gathering on Minimizing Security Challenges Questionnaire" (IIGMSCQ) was used. Cronbach coefficient Alpha method to determine the internal consistency of the IIGMSCQ was used and the reliability coefficient obtained was 0.92. Research Questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and chi-square goodness of fit was used to analyze research hypothesis. The result showed that Intelligence gathering has statistically significant impact on minimizing security challenges in Makurdi local government. Based on the results of this study, it was recommended that Government should implement Intelligence gathering as a mean of elicit relevant security information to minimizing security challenges in the state.

Keywords: National Security, Crime, Insurgency, Conflict, Community

I. INTRODUCTION

Insecurity which has come in different forms as troubles, gruesome murders, robberies by violence, rape, cultism, ritual killings, bribery and official corruption, obtaining goods/money by false pretences, high people kidnapping and abductions, child stealing and kidnapping are bruising more fears to the life of the common people. This is compounded by hunger, unemployment infrastructures and other vices too numerous to mention (Idowu, 2021). Security challenge is a crime that is designed by a set of a wicked people that rendered communities uncondusive for human dwelling.

Regrettably, crime is in its highest peak now in our communities. Idowu (2021) assorted that crime is no more novel, it is rather fulltime job of many Nigerians. Troubles, gruesome murders, robberies by violence, rape, cultism, ritual killings, bribery and official corruption, obtaining goods/money by false pretences, high people kidnapping and abductions, child stealing, religious and political violence associated with gunshot and use of other sophisticated offensive weapon to destroy lives and properties. These endless security challenges are enough to say that our communities are becoming crime injected residents.

These security challenges stem from a combination of factors such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to basic services, and historical ethno-religious tensions. According to Aghedo & Ogunde (2014) assorted that these vulnerabilities make communities susceptible to various security threats, including: armed robbery, cultism activities, communal conflict, gruesome murders, robberies by violence, rape, removal of manhood, ritual killings, bribery and official corruption, obtaining goods/money by false pretences, high people kidnapping and abductions, child stealing and kidnapping.

The issue of Armed Robbery, cultism activities, ritual killing, removed of manhood in our communities is alarming. Both urban and rural areas often lack adequate proper information concerning who involve in such atrocities at presence. The remoteness and limited access to security services needed information in these communities create an environment conducive to criminal activities (Egharevba & Amadasun, 2021).

It seems that every community is facing Communal Conflicts. Communities in Nigeria frequently experience conflicts arising from land disputes, resource allocation, or inter-ethnic rivalries. These conflicts can escalate quickly and result in violence, displacements, and loss of lives (Omosho & Akinlabi, 2018).

Some communities in Nigeria face the threat of insurgency from groups like Boko Haram, which have been responsible for numerous attacks, abductions, kidnapping, raping and destabilization of communities (Aghedo & Osumah, 2019).

In addition, issues of intelligence gathering in Nigeria are treated with flippancy and funds allocated for the assignments, are mostly embezzled, while the agencies personnel are not encouraged to offer their best for the protection of lives and property which always result to intelligence gathering failure and general security catastrophe and fiasco. Another crucial intelligence gathering lacuna in Nigeria and North Bank Makurdi communities in particular is lack of current technology used to intercept and locate mobile and satellite phones used by criminals for intelligence gathering is threatening the security of the nations and the study area in particular.

In some of our residential areas with a significant pastoral population often confront the menace of cattle rustling, where armed bandits steal livestock, leading to economic losses and increased tensions (Ibrahim, 2019). These atrocities, the federal government of Nigeria has

put in place different security agencies such as armed forces, air force, police, civil defense, the Department of State Service (DSS), Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA), the National Intelligence Community (IC) and even with the help of community volunteer guide/ vigilante groups, all is to curb with security challenges but no lasting solution is found. In fact there are many strategies deployed by the Benue state and federal government such as operation Zenda , operation white stripe, operation ayem akpatuman, involvement of youth leaders in various communities (Idowu, 2021). With all these attempts by the government, security challenges in our communities are increasing more. It is on this ground that the researcher wants to investigate if the intelligence gathering will have impact on minimizing the security challenges in our communities in Benue state. Therefore the paper intends to investigate the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in our communities in Benue state, Nigeria.

II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In our society today, both urban and rural communities in Nigeria face significant security challenges, including armed robbery, communal conflicts, insurgency, cultism activities, and cattle rustling and among others.

Despite the fact that the governments of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and that of Benue State have been using government agencies such as armed forces, Civil defense, police, the Department of State Service (DSS), Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA), the National Intelligence Community (IC) and among others with their unreservedly efforts and strategies in other to minimize the security challenges in our communities yet more atrocities are increasing daily (Idowu, 2021). This raised some questions on what could be the problem: does it mean that the security agencies available are not competent enough? Could it be that weapons used by the security agencies are not sophisticated? Could it mean that they are not getting relevant information? This may be that the security agencies available are not have relevant information about who, where, when, what should really the problem. Intelligence gathering highlights the role of early warning and prevention, targeted response, community engagement, strategic planning and resource allocation, intelligence-led investigations, and capacity building (Jackson, 2015). If the security agencies will embrace intelligence gathering practices, our communities may create safer environments for their residents. Segue to this the researcher observed that if Effective intelligence gathering practices will be introduced, it may minimize the security challenges in our communities. Therefore it is on these grounds, that the study seeks to analyse the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in selected community in Makurdi of Benue State.

III. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to assess the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in selected community in North Bank Makurdi of Benue State. The specific objectives are:

- i. To assess the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in the selected communities of North Bank, Makurdi LGA
- ii. To analyze the prompt effort of the government in release of security personnel to address the security challenges.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in North Bank Makurdi Communities of Benue State?
- ii. What is the effort of the government in utilizing intelligence gathering in to addressing the current security challenges?

V. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. Intelligence gathering has no significant impact on minimizing security challenges in Makurdi local government.

Method

The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study was mainly residence of Angwa Ochonu Community, Ajetachi Community, Asase 1 and 2 Community, IDP Camp Community and Court 5 Community in Makurdi, Benue State. The sample size of 200 respondents and the study adopted purposive sampling technique. A self-developed questionnaire called “Impact of Intelligence Gathering on Minimizing Security Challenges Questionnaire” (IIGMSCQ) was used for data collection. Cronbach coefficient Alpha method to determine the internal consistency of the IIGMSCQ and the reliability coefficient obtained was 0.918. Research Questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and chi-square goodness of fit was used to analyze research hypothesis.

VI. RESULTS

Research question one: What is the impact of intelligence gathering on minimizing security challenges in North Bank Makurdi Communities of Benue State?

Table 1: Impact of Intelligence Gathering on Minimizing Security Challenges

SN	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Intelligence gathering activities is the means of causing peace in the community	200	3.30	.65	High Impact
2	Its help to arrest the insurgencies and set community at peace	200	3.23	.50	High Impact
3	Intelligence gathering is a good programme for peace keeping	200	3.22	.49	High Impact
4	Surety agencies through intelligence gathering minimizes sporadically arrest of innocent souls	200	3.67	.51	High Impact
5	Through this platform, many criminal activities and others atrocities have reduced in our community	200	3.38	.49	High Impact

Table 1 shows that the items ranging from 1 to 5 with their respective mean (\bar{X}) of 3.30, 3.23, 3.22, 3.67 and 3.38 with the standard deviation (SD) of .65, .50, .49, .51 and .49 respectively. The remark depicts that all the items were good and have high impact. Therefore, the intelligence gathering has very high impact on minimizing security challenges in North Bank Makurdi Communities of Benue State.

Research Question two: What is the effort of the government in utilizing intelligence gathering in to addressing the current security challenges?

Table 2: Effort of the Government in Utilizing Intelligence Gathering in Addressing the Current Security Challenges

SN	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
6	Government has provided modern technological gadgets for effective intelligence gathering	200	1.34	.90	Disagreed
7	Government has embark on training the security agencies on how to collecting via intelligence gathering imperative	200	1.24	.81	Disagreed
8	Government has released funds to support security agencies on effective data gathering	200	1.23	.91	Disagreed
9	Government have creates effective sensitization to communities on security challenges so that fact can be collected	200	1.65	.88	Disagreed
10	Government have set security stand-bye for maintain peace in the affected communities.	200	2.30	.97	Disagreed

Table 2 shows that the items ranging from 6 to 10 with their respective mean (\bar{X}) of 1.34, 1.24, 1.23, 1.65 and 2.30 with the standard deviation (SD) of .90, .81, .91, .88 and .97 respectively. The remark depicts that all the mean score of the items were below anchor point of 2.50, so were disagreed. Therefore, the finding showed that Government has not provided modern technological gadgets, no security training on how gather information, has no released funds to support security agencies and no security stand-bye for maintain peace for effective intelligence gathering.

Results of Analysis of Chi-square on hypothesis One

Intelligence gathering has no significant impact on minimizing security challenges in Makurdi local government

Table 3: Chi-square analysis on the Impact of Intelligence Gathering on Minimizing Security Challenges

χ^2 -cal	df	Asymp. sig	N	level of sign.	remarks
101.450	3	.000	200	.05	rejected

In table 3 above, the χ^2 -cal - value is 101.450, while the significant levels of .05 with 3 degree of freedom yielded the Asymp. Sig. of .000 using SPSS-Computer Analysis, since significance value of 0.05 is greater than the Asymp.sig value of 0.000 (i.e. $0.05 > 0.000$) the null hypothesis is rejected in the analysis. Therefore, the result shows that Intelligence gathering has statistical significant impact on minimizing security challenges in Makurdi local government.

VII. MAJOR FINDINGS

Based on the research, the following findings were made:

1. Intelligence gathering has very high impact on minimizing security challenges in North Bank Makurdi Communities of Benue State.
2. Government has not provided modern technological gadgets, no security training on how to gather information, has no released funds to support security agencies and no security stand-bye for maintain peace for effective intelligence gathering.
3. Intelligence gathering has statistical significant impact on minimizing security challenges in Makurdi local government.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Intelligence gathering plays a pivotal role in Nigeria's security, socio-economic development, and evidence-based decision-making. By recognizing the impact of intelligence gathering approaches, Nigeria can enhance its intelligence capabilities, effectively address security challenges, and promote sustainable development. Implementing the proposed strategies will greatly contribute to a safer and a more prosperous Nigeria.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should implement Intelligence gathering as a mean of elicit relevant security information to minimizing security challenges in the state.
2. Government should provide modern technological gadgets, security training on how to gather information, to released funds to support security agencies and also security stand-bye for maintain peace for effective intelligence gathering.

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